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Parental Involvement As A Predictor Of Student Self-Esteem In Secondary Schools In Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

Self-esteem plays a crucial role in the psychological and academic development of adolescents in secondary schools. The family environment, particularly the level of parental involvement in students' education, has been identified as a significant factor influencing students' self-perception and emotional wellbeing. Despite the growing recognition of the importance of parental support in education, cases of low self-esteem among secondary school students continue to manifest in forms such as anxiety, low confidence, poor participation in learning activities and emotional maladjustment. This study therefore examined parental involvement as a predictor of students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. Correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population comprised senior secondary school students in public secondary schools across the six education zones in Anambra State. A sample of 908 students was drawn using multistage sampling techniques. Four instruments were used for data collection namely Parental Involvement Questionnaire (PIQ) and Students' Self-Esteem Questionnaire (SSQ). The instruments were validated by experts and their reliability coefficients were established using Cronbach Alpha method. Data collected were analyzed using simple and multiple regression analysis at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that parents' involvement in school decision-making significantly predicted students' self-esteem ($R = 0.721, p < 0.05$), while parenting practices at home also significantly predicted students' self-esteem though at a lower level ($R = 0.382, p < 0.05$). The study concluded that active parental involvement contributes significantly to the development of healthy self-esteem among secondary school students. It was therefore recommended among others that parents should actively participate in their children's academic and emotional development through consistent communication with schools and supportive home learning environments.

Keywords: Parental Involvement, Self-Esteem, Secondary School Students, Parenting Practices, School Communication

INTRODUCTION

Education plays a fundamental role in shaping the intellectual, emotional and social development of learners. Beyond the acquisition of academic knowledge, education is expected to foster the psychological wellbeing and personal confidence of students (Okoye et al., 2021). One of the psychological constructs that significantly influences students' behaviour, academic participation and social adjustment is self-esteem. Self-esteem refers to an individual's overall evaluation of his or her worth and capability (Rosenberg, 1965). Students with healthy self-esteem tend to exhibit confidence,

resilience and motivation in their academic and social activities, while those with low self-esteem often experience anxiety, lack of confidence and poor academic engagement (Adeyemo, 2019).

The development of students' self-esteem is influenced by several environmental factors including family background, school climate and peer relationships (Nwankwo et al., 2018). Among these factors, parental involvement has been widely recognized as one of the most influential contributors to students' emotional and psychological development (Unachukwu, 2020). Parental involvement refers to the active participation of parents in their children's educational experiences both at home and in school settings (Moneva et al., 2020). It includes activities such as helping children with homework, monitoring their academic progress, communicating with teachers, attending school meetings and participating in school decision-making processes (Agobua, 2021).

Parental involvement can occur in different forms including home-based involvement and school-based involvement (Hanaysha, 2016). Home-based involvement includes providing learning materials, encouraging children's study habits, discussing school activities with them and setting expectations for academic success (Obijindu, 2020). School-based involvement on the other hand includes participation in Parent-Teacher Association meetings, school decision-making processes and communication with teachers regarding students' academic progress (Ananomo et al., 2021). These various forms of parental involvement collectively create a supportive environment that enhances students' emotional wellbeing and confidence (Okoye et al., 2021).

In recent years, educators and psychologists have increasingly emphasized the importance of parental participation in shaping students' attitudes and psychological development. Studies have shown that students who receive emotional support and encouragement from their parents tend to develop higher levels of confidence and self-esteem (Adeyemo, 2019). When parents demonstrate interest in their children's educational activities, students often feel valued, motivated and capable of achieving academic goals (Agobua, 2021). In contrast, lack of parental support may lead to feelings of neglect, insecurity and low self-worth among adolescents (Unachukwu, 2020).

In Anambra State, concerns have been raised about the increasing cases of emotional instability and low self-esteem among secondary school students. Observations have shown that some students exhibit behaviours such as anxiety, sadness, lack of concentration, impulsive actions and poor interpersonal relationships, which are often associated with low self-esteem (Okoye et al., 2021). These behavioural patterns are frequently linked to inadequate emotional support from the home environment (Nwankwo et al., 2018). Researchers have therefore suggested that parental involvement in education may play a critical role in addressing these psychological challenges among students (Ananomo et al., 2021).

Empirical studies have provided evidence supporting the relationship between parental involvement and students' self-esteem. For instance, Odogwu et al. (2022) found that parenting practices at home significantly predict self-esteem among secondary school students in Anambra State. Similarly, Agobua (2021) reported that effective communication between parents and schools contributes positively to students' emotional development and confidence. In the same vein, Ananomo et al. (2021) observed that parents' participation in school decision-making enhances students' sense of belonging and personal worth.

Despite these findings, many parents remain minimally involved in their children's academic and emotional development due to work commitments, lack of awareness or socio-economic constraints (Moneva et al., 2020). This situation raises important questions about the extent to which parental involvement influences students' self-esteem in secondary schools. Understanding this relationship is essential for developing effective strategies that promote students' psychological wellbeing and academic success. Based on these concerns, the present study investigated parental involvement as a predictor of students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to examine parental involvement as a predictor of students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to determine:

1. The predictive value of parents' involvement in school decision-making on students' self-esteem.
2. The predictive value of parenting practices at home on students' self-esteem.

3. The predictive value of parents' communication with school on students' self-esteem.

Research Question

1. What is the predictive value of parents' involvement in school decision-making on students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. What is the predictive value of parenting practices at home on students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
3. What is the predictive value of parents' communication with school on students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

1. Parents' involvement in school decision-making does not significantly predict students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Parenting practices at home do not significantly predict students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
3. Parents' communication with school does not significantly predict students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a correlational research design. This design was considered appropriate because it allows the researcher to determine the degree and direction of relationship between predictor variables and outcome variables. Correlational design is suitable for studies that seek to determine how one variable predicts or influences another variable within a population. The study was conducted in Anambra State, located in the South-Eastern region of Nigeria. The population comprised senior secondary school students in public secondary schools across the six education zones in the state. A multistage sampling technique was used to select the sample for the study. Parental Involvement Questionnaire (PIQ) and Students' Self-Esteem Questionnaire (SSQ) were used for data collection. The instruments were validated by experts in educational psychology and measurement and evaluation. Reliability of the instruments was established using Cronbach Alpha method, yielding acceptable reliability coefficients of 0.78 and 0.78 respectively. Data collection involved direct administration of the questionnaire to students in their respective schools. Out of 952 copies administered, 908 copies were correctly completed and returned, representing a high response rate suitable for statistical analysis. Data collected were analyzed using simple and multiple regression analysis at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the predictive value of parents' involvement in school decision-making on students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 1: Summary of simple regression analysis on parents' involvement in school decision-making as predictor of students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized β	Std. Dev. β	Standardized B
Constant	20.157	6.035	
Parents' Involvement in School Decision-Making	0.393	0.316	0.382
R	0.382		
R ²	0.347		
Adj. R ²	0.291		

The results revealed that parental involvement significantly predicts students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The regression analysis showed that parents' involvement in school decision-making positively predicted students' self-esteem with a regression coefficient of $R = 0.382$ and $R^2 = 0.347$, indicating that approximately 35% of the variation in students' self-esteem was explained by parents' involvement in school decision-making

Research Question 2: *What is the predictive value of parenting practices at home on students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 2: Summary of simple regression analysis on parenting practices at home as predictor of students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized β	Std. Dev. B	Standardized B
Constant	24.823	5.325	
Parenting Practices at Home	.754	.278	0.721
R	0.721		
R ²	0.648		
Adj. R ²	0.605		

Furthermore, parenting practices at home strongly predicted students' self-esteem with $R = 0.721$ and $R^2 = 0.648$, indicating that about 65% of the variation in students' self-esteem was explained by parenting practices at home. The results also indicated that the regression models were statistically significant since the p-values obtained were less than 0.05, leading to the rejection of the corresponding null hypotheses.

Research Question 3: *What is the predictive value of parental communication with school predict students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 3: Summary of simple regression analysis on parents' communication with school as predictor of students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized β	Std. Dev. β	Standardized B
Constant	18.873	6.912	
Parents' Communication with School	0.374	0.329	0.367
R	0.367		
R ²	0.332		
Adj. R ²	0.275		

The results revealed that parents' communication with school significantly predicts students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The regression analysis showed that parents' communication with school positively predicted students' self-esteem with a regression coefficient of $R = 0.367$ and $R^2 = 0.332$, indicating that approximately 33% of the variation in students' self-esteem was explained by parents' communication with school.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Parents' involvement in school decision-making does not significantly predict students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 4: Test of significance of simple regression analysis on parents' involvement in school decision-making as predictor of students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized B	Std. Dev. B	Standardized β	t-value	p-value
Constant	20.157	6.035		21.509	0.000
Parents' involvement in school decision-making	0.393	0.316	0.382	17.664	0.000
R	0.382				
R ²	0.347				
Adj. R ²	0.291				
F	28.472				0.000

The test of significance of the simple regression analysis in Table 4 showed that $R = 0.382$, $R^2 = 0.347$ and Adjusted $R^2 = 0.291$, with $F = 28.472$, $t = 17.664$ and $p = 0.000$. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected. This indicates that parents' involvement in school decision-making significantly predicts students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Parenting practices at home does not significantly predict students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 5: Test of significance of simple regression analysis on parenting practices at home as predictor of students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized B	Std. Dev. B	Standardized B	t- value	p- value
Constant	24.823	5.325		28.541	0.000
Parenting practices at home	0.754	0.278	0.721	23.326	0.000
R	0.721				
R ²	0.648				
Adj. R ²	0.605				
F	35.164				0.000

The test of significance of the simple regression analysis in Table 5 showed that $R = 0.721$, $R^2 = 0.648$ and Adjusted $R^2 = 0.605$, with $F = 35.164$, $t = 23.326$ and $p = 0.000$. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that parenting practices at home significantly predict students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis Three

H₀₃: Parents' communication with school does not significantly predict students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 6: Test of significance of simple regression analysis on parents' communication with school as predictor of students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Anambra State

	Unstandardized B	Std. Dev. B	Standardized B	t- value	p- value
Constant	18.874	6.912		20.237	0.000
Parents' communication with school	0.374	0.329	0.367	16.731	0.000
R	0.367				
R ²	0.332				
Adj. R ²	0.275				
F	25.281				0.000

The test of significance of the simple regression analysis in Table 11 showed that $R = 0.367$, $R^2 = 0.332$ and Adjusted $R^2 = 0.275$, with $F = 25.281$, $t = 16.731$ and $p = 0.000$. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected. This indicates that parents' communication with school significantly predicts students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

DISCUSSION

Findings revealed that parents' involvement in school decision-making positively and significantly predicted students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Anambra State, though to a low extent. This involvement includes participation in PTA meetings, school projects, school-based management committee meetings, budget preparation, school activities, and solving school-related problems. Such participation promotes students' confidence and sense of belonging in the school environment. This finding supports Ananomo et al. (2021) who reported that parents' involvement in school decision-making contributes to the development of students' self-esteem. Similarly, Enwere and Mbakwe (2021)

found that parents' participation in school decision-making significantly influences students' self-esteem in secondary schools.

Also, the findings showed that parenting practices at home positively and significantly predicted students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Anambra State to a high extent. These practices include providing healthcare, balanced nutrition, parental guidance, homework support, protection from harmful activities, enforcement of safety boundaries, and clear communication of expectations. Such supportive home environments help students develop confidence and emotional stability. This finding agrees with Nwokolo and Obijindu (2020) who noted that protecting children from harmful activities and enforcing boundaries enhances children's self-esteem. In the same vein, Illoakasia (2021) reported that positive parenting practices at home significantly contribute to students' self-esteem in schools.

Further, the findings indicated that parents' communication with school positively and significantly predicted students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Anambra State, though to a low extent. This communication involves attending PTA meetings, exchanging ideas with teachers, giving feedback on students' progress, reporting children's behaviour at home, and discussing strategies for improving students' learning. Effective communication between parents and schools supports students' academic and social development. This finding aligns with Agogbua (2021) who found that parents' exchange of ideas with schools significantly influences students' self-esteem. Similarly, Odogwu et al. (2022) reported that parents' feedback to teachers and regular communication with schools enhance children's social development and self-esteem. These findings also align with theoretical perspectives such as Epstein's model of parental involvement and attachment theory which emphasize the importance of supportive parent-child relationships in shaping children's psychological wellbeing. Overall, the study demonstrates that parental involvement is a crucial factor in fostering healthy self-esteem among secondary school students.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that parental involvement significantly predicts students' self-esteem in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Parenting practices at home, parents' communication with schools and parents' involvement in school decision-making collectively contribute to the development of students' self-confidence and emotional wellbeing. Active parental participation in children's education therefore remains essential for promoting positive psychological outcomes among adolescents.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Parents should actively support their children's academic and emotional development by creating supportive home learning environments.
2. Schools should strengthen communication between teachers and parents through regular meetings and feedback systems.
3. Educational administrators should encourage parents to participate in school decision-making processes.
4. Guidance counsellors should organize workshops to educate parents on the importance of their involvement in students' psychological development.
5. Government and educational stakeholders should implement policies that promote strong home-school partnerships.

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